

Towards a Heterogeneous Common/Shared Storage System Architecture

Michael F. Shields
National Security Agency
Ft. Meade, MD

Abstract

Storage management for our scientific, general, and signals processing complexes in the past has been addressed on a system-by-system, complex-by-complex basis. Over the years, the time-phased introduction of a wide variety of heterogeneous computer systems, each of which was selected to solve a unique operational problem, has created a most challenging environment from the storage management perspective. Each processor had its own dedicated storage subsystems, and in the main, its own custom-software solution to its storage management. A walking tour of our major complexes would expose one of almost every type of computer and almost every imaginable data-processing application type, each with its own robotic tape and disk subsystems. Our current challenge is to design and implement a coherent mass storage architecture (across all of the processing complexes) that is flexible, repartitionable, and easier to manage. We are in the midst of that challenge now. From the 1970s to the present, our approach to storage has changed considerably, shaped in large measure by the products that have arisen in the commercial marketplace. This paper discusses our corporate adaptation to change and presents our current strategy in this vital area of high-performance/high-capacity computing.

Mass storage acquisition strategy

Custom era

Throughout the 1970s and for most of the 1980s, NSA was forced to develop custom solutions to our high-end storage requirements. We consistently developed custom robotic tape and custom in-house software file-serving systems to satisfy the ever-growing needs of our user community. As late as 1988, this approach manifested itself into yet another custom, large-scale, high-performance, high-capacity mass storage system (MSS) acquisition. By 1988, our existing storage systems had reached the end of their useful life, and the original vendors no longer manufactured the required

components. Our high-end computer complex was predominately Cray, and industry had no commercial technology available to solve our storage performance and capacity requirements. Concept-definition studies were awarded to five different vendors; the studies concluded that our diversity problem could be solved with the integration of technologies just entering the marketplace. Our architectural goal was to develop a large robotic tape file-server system that would be shared by a large number of client systems. This central approach was deemed to be both feasible and the most cost-effective solution. We had two key goals which were equally important to the success of this effort: the first was to satisfy our operational requirements with a custom solution; the second was to create incentives for industry to commercialize this system and to develop other solutions that could satisfy medium- and even low-performance MSS requirements. We believed that this effort would be a failure if both goals were not realized. To minimize risk, we specified that two releases be delivered. The first would use commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) components to demonstrate the proof-of-concept. We would use this limited capability system to develop lessons learned, which would be factored into the design of the second system. The second system would employ a modular design for the robotic tape subsystem, which would facilitate future growth in both capacity and performance. This system would use helical scan drives with data rates and cassette capacities significantly greater than any known data-processing peripherals in the marketplace at that time. The file server selected was a mini-supercomputer, and the software was totally customized and based on the user's specific requirements. We continued this approach until mid-1992 and gained valuable lessons, which caused significant changes in our evolving acquisition strategy.

Lessons learned

The principal lesson learned in our custom era was to never again enter into a custom MSS development effort. These efforts are always more costly in both dollars and time than

even pessimistic estimates. Other factors contributing to this conclusion were:

- custom operating system (OS) hooks used to aid in system performance made porting of the software very difficult;
- configuration control of the components and subsystems made upgrades difficult and problem resolution a significant challenge;
- lack of established standards impeded technology insertions into the system architecture;
- vendor personnel retention jeopardized schedules, system support, and system enhancement;
- use of a COTS relational database imposed scaling limitations when used in an MSS;
- skill levels required by user and support organizations exceeded even our expectations; and,
- support costs far exceeded anyone's expectations.

Migration to COTS

By mid-1992, system-level MSS products were commercially available for the mid-range and low-end requirements. MSS standards were either published or being developed, and industry was starting to build products to these standards. A wide variety of commercial robotics and tape drives were commercially available and vendor product plans indicated that their next generation of drives/robotics (available in the CY 94/95 timeframe) could satisfy our high-end (100+ TBs) storage requirements. Considering our investment to date in a custom, large robotic tape file-server solution, we altered our strategy to buy only COTS solutions from this point forward. Our existing contracts were modified to conform to this approach. Another significant factor in this decision was the increased dependence on the STK Silo. While the custom solution was struggling through the development and integration process, we were forced to acquire Silos to satisfy increased Cray storage demands. Silos were initially dedicated on a one-to-one basis with supercomputers; however, the need to share access between systems pushed us to create a unique Silo cluster approach to preclude any single point of failure in the tape path. Figure 1 depicts this approach; it has been defined previously in a paper presented at the NASA MSS Conference last year. Other factors contributing to the major switch in our acquisition approach are: high reliability and product upgrade plans for robotics and drives; emergence of the AMASS software product as the preferred low-end product of choice; maturation of standards; and, most importantly, the fielding of system-level MSS products, some of which could even satisfy the performance and capacity requirements specified in our 1988 custom development effort. During this timeframe, a number of low- and medium-end

MSS system solutions were fielded throughout our user community to satisfy an ever-increasing storage requirement. By late 1994, almost every major acquisition plan contained the requirement for some form of mass storage.

1995 and beyond

As a result of the successes of the early 1990s, we have continued to refine our acquisition strategy and approach. Even now, there are some high-end MSS COTS offerings, and more on the drawing board. We have chosen to use our limited influence by encouraging computer OEMS to qualify selected drives and robotics with the desired file- and volume-serving software products to increase the number of COTS alternatives. We have emphasized this approach to avoid custom OS hooks, if at all possible, in order to facilitate portability of software between platforms. We stress the portability of storage solutions consistent with our heterogeneous open-system architecture. We have established a central clearinghouse for evaluating MSS technology and have shared this information throughout our agency. Upon request, we have also provided data to other government agencies. Within the scientific processing community, we have established a group consisting of ADP and user decision makers to coordinate all buy-decisions for storage products used in the scientific architecture. This group oversees the established cycle to track, identify, acquire, and evaluate MSS products prior to placing them into production. We focus on scalability, supportability, platform portability, performance, and cost. Finally, we have moved away from the single large-library concept of the 1980s and have a clear focus on the logical-library concept, consisting of many physically distributed smaller systems. We have made every attempt to minimize organizational duplication of effort in this process and have selected products that are "system-level" and supported by either a computer company or system-level integrator. All products must have an architecture that facilitates technology insertions/upgrades.

Storage architectural plans

To understand our storage plans, it is essential to consider the three major processing areas, each of which is quite different in its equipment mix, performance and capacity requirements, and infrastructure.

Scientific processing

Today, the scientific area is almost synonymous with Cray and MPPs. We are moving away from a Cray-centric architecture and toward a truly heterogeneous one; Cray will still be the major high-end processing resource for some time, however. With respect to the Cray processor installation,

Figure 1.

we have attempted to move away from a dedicated application to a dedicated system-processing paradigm. Over the past five years, we have attempted to treat all Crays as merely part of our high-end resources to enable applications to run on available processors, whenever practical. Because the specific configurations vary widely in capability, this is not always possible; however, the majority of our applications can be executed on a number of the Cray configurations. To satisfy the movement of data to the most available processor, we have taken a number of steps in the storage arena to facilitate this effort. Last year we installed a number of ND14 HiPPI-connected RAID disks, so that any Cray with HiPPI peripheral connectivity to the switch has a physical path to the data. However, this reallocation had to be done under system-administrator control. We are currently testing Cray's shared file system (SFS) software in conjunction with the ND14 and the bus-based gateway in an attempt to share disk data more efficiently. We are attempting to minimize acquisition of dedicated disks for each system as our capacity requirements grow. User home directories will be moved to several Auspex servers later this year. In addition, we will acquire NFS 3.0 for our Crays in an attempt to increase performance for NFS-mounted file systems. Other NFS servers that may deliver higher performance/capacity are being considered for acquisition. These include the MaxStrat Gen5 ProFile product and the SGI product. Once again, the principal goal is to minimize the acquisition of storage that is dedicated to a single processor and/or is processor-unique. In addition, we intend to acquire one ND41 HiPPI/ATM/Fibrechannel

disk array during CY95. This product is very similar to the MaxStrat ProFile product and provides for increased network connectivity, capacity, and performance for our shared-disk inventory. The attractive feature of this product is that it could be used with other compute resources and be modified to be used as an NFS server, if desired.

Regarding tape storage, we will continue to rely upon the STK Silo clusters as our principal tertiary storage repository for all processors. We are about midway to completion with the insertion of long tape (800 MB) cartridges into our Silos, all of which have 36 track drives. It is important to note that our Silos act as Cray volume servers, not file servers, and that we do not use DMF. The principal architectural piece that allows us to manage such a large library structure was made possible by the creation of a metadata management system, which we refer to as the DMS. The DMS is used as the principal access method to determine which files stored on the STK Silos are to be loaded onto the Crays/MPPs for processing. The DMS consists of multiple Sun 4/690 processors running Sybase. The metadata is stored on these processors at the same time that files are moved to tape on the Silos. Each Sun supports a discrete user group that generates queries regarding files of interest, based on the metadata that is unique to their organization. Jim Berry's paper in another section of the proceedings provides more insight into this capability. By using the STK Silos as volume servers, data access is provided in a more timely fashion than by the file-server approach.

Our tape evaluation plans for CY95 include the acquisition of STK D3 drives for one Silo. Based upon

Figure 2.

performance, reliability, and remote monitoring capabilities, a production decision will be made regarding the specific role that this technology will play in our tape architecture. In addition, we intend to evaluate the IBM NTP tape product in two different robotic libraries. One will be the IBM 3495, as depicted in Figure 2, and the other will be the EMASS AML/2. Both libraries are being qualified by Cray and other high-end computer companies, while smaller versions of each are being qualified by a number of server class computer companies. As soon as these systems are qualified by Cray, both configurations will be tested at NSA as volume servers. Based on the in-house testing results, production decisions will be made in CY96.

Regarding server class storage, another interesting development over the past several years has been the rapid growth in performance for Unix servers. Many of the problems processed heretofore on Cray-class machines can now be ported to relatively inexpensive Unix servers; this has fueled the architectural migration from Cray-centric. High-end servers such as the SGI Power Challenge, DEC Alpha, for example, have proven to be dependable scientific processing resources. As such, the requirement to match high-performance RAID disk and robotic tape to such platforms has taken a front seat. As a result of progress made during 1994 and based on technology forecasts, we are currently evaluating several system-level, server-class MSS products this year. Currently under evaluation is the SGI Challenge running the AMASS software. Three different robotic tape libraries will be evaluated. They include DLT, Exabyte Mammoth, and IBM NTP drives. In addition to evaluating the suitability of these drive technologies as part of an MSS, it is our goal to determine price/performance points for low-, medium-, and high-performance robotic tape systems. These systems will be used in a variety of application areas, to include: front-end data handling hubs, pure storage systems, and as database machines with mass storage. Additionally, a test is under way to determine the

suitability of this platform as an NFS 3.0 server. It is interesting to note that the preponderance of the storage products to be evaluated for the scientific processing area are server-class—a marked deviation from previous years.

General processing

Today, the general processing area is synonymous with IBM/plugin-compatible systems. But from a tape-storage perspective and from an architectural view, a common family of drives and robotics prevails. The principal robotic tape system supporting production today is the STK Silo. This complex employs IBM's System Managed Storage (SMS) for the majority of systems, while the majority of the Silos use 18 track drives/controllers and utilize ESCON and Block Mux connectivity to the drives. Since this architecture is not germane to the open-systems arena, this paper will discuss only those products and plans that use similar components and subsystems as outlined in the architectural plans. Currently, our management guidance is for all complexes to use the same storage components whenever practical. With respect to disk, EMC, heretofore an IBM/plugin-compatible vendor, has branched out into the open-systems marketplace. The general processing element is currently evaluating an EMC RAID disk array. The scientific and signals processing elements are also tracking that technology. However, in the tape arena, there is a rich overlap of products that are applicable to all complexes: For example, the general processing group is evaluating the IBM 3494/3490E library using the open-systems storage software product ADSM. This effort is of interest from both the hardware and software perspectives. ADSM is being ported to the SGI platform and other open-systems servers and might have potential applicability in other complexes. The IBM 3494 robotic library and its performance, capacity, and reliability-testing results are fully germane to all other

Figure 3.

open-systems efforts. Later this year, that system will receive IBM 3590 drives which will make it complementary from an architectural perspective to the corporate storage plan.

It is important to note that the general processing group is one of the key participants in the overall processing architecture group and that their storage plans are consistent with the open-systems architecture to the maximum extent possible. They actively participate in the storage-technology tracking process, and share in data exchange for common items being evaluated and for common products already in production (for example, STK Silos).

Signals processing

For the past two years, the scientific and signals processing elements have worked together very closely with respect to storage architecture. With the rapid rise of digitization, the processing performance and capacity requirements have greatly increased. The server-class storage section above reflects the types of activities that are germane to this portion of the processing architecture. With the rise in server capabilities, the need for rapid, reliable storage has increased significantly. The principal deep-storage system in use today is a medium-performance, medium-capacity fileserving MSS system as depicted in Figure 3. It is Convex-based and uses the EMASS FileServ commercial software product. The robotic library is an STK Powderhorn Silo with 36-track, long-tape (800 MB) cassettes. It is connected to a diverse group of servers via FDDI and is used to sup-

port their current mass storage needs. This system will be replaced in mid-CY96 with a 150-TB EMASS AML/2-IBM 3590 library. The control processor will be replaced with a significantly improved Unix SMP server running the EMASS commercial file-serving software. Connectivity will be via HiPPI, ATM, and FDDI to an ever-increasing set of high-performance servers. In addition, during late CY95 and early '96 many new data-handling front-end servers and storage systems will be installed, all of which are consistent with our architectural plans.

To insure architectural consistency, the signals processing element is one of the key participants in the processing architectural working group. They, too, will use all of the same family of physical storage components as the other groups, wherever possible. They will also lever off of product evaluations from the server-class storage-testing efforts currently under way, principally the SGI/AMASS/IBM 3590 effort (see Figure 4). They will perform technology insertions to extend the useful life of existing systems, where it makes sense, by the addition of DLT and Exabyte Mammoth technology where possible. Of principal utility to this group will be to ingest metadata management solutions to facilitate user access to the ever-increasing volumes of data.

Architectural considerations

The ultimate goal of our storage architecture is to create a framework in which any authorized user can easily access any data, regardless of where it is located, in a rapid fashion. Even though the diverse installed base and the lack of software with which to achieve this goal will not be

Figure 4.

available for some time, it is critical to develop an architectural framework in which this process can be developed and later supported. To that end, we have begun the move toward that goal.

The following discussion will help the reader understand our environment and more importantly the rationale as to why we have chosen this course. We believe that the overall process will be long and painful, but that portions are achievable with the architectural discipline that is being implemented. The following elements are key for us to realize even a portion of our overall goals.

- (1) The scalability of our preferred HSM (AMASS) is key to its expanded use in both the signals and scientific processing complexes.
- (2) All of our storage servers (both file- and volume-serving) and their robotic tape subsystems must be capable of remote monitoring by our Consolidated Command Center's preferred software product, the Boole and Babbage Command Post.
- (3) All storage systems must be capable of lights-out operations and degraded-mode operation. This includes drive monitoring, cassette durability, automated head cleaning, and statistical visibility to the command center.
- (4) All storage systems will be co-located in CY97 to our new Computer Center Building. The systems must be accessible via high-speed networks to our diverse user community located throughout the campus.
- (5) We desire, to the maximum extent possible, that all computer and storage resources allow reallocation. Ultimately we would desire dynamic reallocation by the operating system, as in SMS.
- (6) Our architecture must allow for both volume- and file-serving systems as needed to support production.

- (7) Software, or the lack thereof, is considered to be the high-risk area in achieving our goals.
- (8) NSA will continue to track promising efforts by other government and commercial organizations, for example, HPSS and AFS/DFS. "Not invented here" is a recipe for disaster.

Summary

Our approach should be clear as we have standardized on three different robotic tape systems for our high-end processors across our three compute complexes. These are IBM 3494/3495, EMASS AML/2, and STK4400 Silos. The drives used with these robotics include: IBM/STK 36 track, IBM 3590, and D3. For our server-class systems, we have a similar approach as outlined in the list above. The principal common entity for the server-class problem is the AMASS HSM product. The specific drive/robotics and platform will be selected based on the required performance and capacity. Regarding high-performance file servers, we will evaluate the scalability of both the EMASS FileServ and AMASS products during early CY96 and make our decision regarding its suitability for 150+ TB libraries. Our ultimate goal for the future would be to have one logically shared, multiple-system, robotic-tape library, accessible by any of our compute complexes. We view the principal risk in achieving our goals to be in the area of software.

We have established a processing-architecture steering group with key participation from the major processing complexes. We have established a clearinghouse for tracking technology and have started a viable product evaluation plan. Data is shared freely among our various groups and with selected government agencies. We have established a working group to recommend acquisition of storage

systems to satisfy operational needs and to prioritize our process. We have established a discipline that facilitates technology insertions and ties products to our capacity and performance requirements from a corporate perspective. Finally, we are attempting to address not only storage but also metadata management as an integral part of the system level

solution. Centralized Command Center operations and remote monitoring of lights-out storage are fundamental to our approach. While we have a long way to go, these steps will enable us to address the problem in a cohesive, integrated fashion.